

Supplementary material 1

Table 1s. *Ae. tauschii* accessions

Accession	Subspecies*	Country**	Locality***	Longitude	Latitude
				(Decimal)	
t 1	t	Russia	Dagestan, 3 km from Gedzhuh v. to Ersy v., 120 m	48.07	42.09
t 2	s		Dagestan, 4 km from Ersy to Gedzhuh, 200 m	48.04	42.07
t 6s	s		Dagestan, vicinity of Rukel v., 380 m	48.24	41.98
t 9(1)s	s		Dagestan, eastern slope of hill “336”, 250 m	48.29	42.00
k 362	t		Dagestan, vicinity of Novolakskoye v.	46.49	43.11
k 1025	s		Dagestan, Derbent – Kuba road, 19 m	48.31	42.00
k 1770	s		Dagestan, vicinity of Kasumkent v., 630 m	48.11	41.67
AE 725	t		N Ossetia, 10 km S of Ordzhonikidze	44.65	42.87
k 608	t	Georgia	Marneuli d., Marneuli – Tbilisi road, 530 m	44.77	41.55
k 612	s		Gori d., vicinity of Rene v., 750 m	44.09	41.91
k 1216	t		Aspindza d., 1000 m	43.25	41.58
k 1792	s		Ambrolauri d.	43.14	42.51

AE 929	s		Mccheta, Dzvari, S slope, 550 m	44.68	41.84
AE 1037	s		20 km NW Citeli-Ckaro, 1000 m	45.89	41.62
t 18	t	Armenia	50 km from Sisian to Azizbekov, turn to Dzhermuk, 1400 m	45.56	39.69
t 34	s		5 km from Kafan to Goris, 1000 m	46.31	39.22
t 39	s		At SE entrance to Goris, 1300 m	46.35	39.48
k 1185	s		Abovyan d., vicinity of Gehard, 1660 m	44.78	40.15
AE 476	t		Erebuni	44.65	40.19
KU 2824	t		1 km S of Bjurakan	44.26	40.32
AL 8-78	s				
t 13	s	Azerbaijan	1.5 km from Maraza v. to Hilmilli v., 1000 m	48.88	40.64
t 15	s		Vicinity of Tirdjan v. (the road to Ismailli), 760 m	48.34	40.76
t 26	s		At entrance to Dzhebrail (from Fizuli), 580 m	47.03	39.41
k 106	s		Pushkino d., Bellusvar frontier post, 130 m	48.38	39.38
k 108	s		Massali d., Muskyudzha v., Chapayev collective farm, 100 m	48.65	39.00
k 109	s		Astrahanbazar d., Novogolovnya v., 90 m	48.57	39.21
k 124	s		Shemaha d., collective farm №3, 630 m	48.64	40.63

k 141	s		Near Kutkashen, 600 m	47.83	40.95
k 169	s		Zakatali experiment station, 570 m	46.65	41.64
k 296	s		Vartashen d., Yakubli v., 600 m	47.45	40.91
k 336	s		Lachin d., Karnkaha v., 1300 m	46.54	39.66
k 493	s		Stepanokert d., vicinity of Chanahchi v., 1100 m	46.83	39.70
k 616	t		SE of Shamhor	46.07	40.80
AE 723	t		20 km S of Scheki	47.14	41.01
k 1038	s		Kuba d., Velvelichay river valley, 800 m	48.62	41.31
k 1099	s		10 km from Lerik to Lenkoran	48.50	38.80
k 1552	s		Dzhalilabad d., Lyaken frontier post, 410 m	48.30	39.11
k 1782	t		Kusari d., Hudat v.	48.42	41.46
k 1866	s		Zangelan d., Ordakni v., 800 m	46.61	39.04
AE 224	s		Divichi d., Bilidzhi v.	48.86	41.19
k 1954	t	Iran (c)	26 km from Shirat, 1300 m	47.20	37.91
k 1956s	s		Near Maku, 850 m	44.83	39.29
k 1961	s		Tage-Boston, 1400 m	47.07	34.28

KU 20-7	s	2 km N of Karaj (Suburbs of Teheran)	51.00	35.82
KU 2071	t	2 km N of Karaj (Suburbs of Teheran)	51.00	35.82
KU 20-8	s	25 km WSW of Firuzkuh	52.53	35.65
KU 2112	s	19 km SW of Ardabil (Ardabil - Surab)	48.14	38.14
KU 2113	t	Suburbs of Mahabad	45.73	36.86
KU 2116	t	32 km S of Khoy (Rezaiyeh - Khoy)	44.83	38.32
KU 2118	s	Khoy	44.96	38.55
KU 2121	t	42 km NW of Tabriz (Khoy - Tabriz)	45.91	38.33
KU 2123	s	Tabriz	46.29	38.08
KU 2142	t	16.4 km E from Maku to Khoy, 1200 m	44.67	39.27
KU 2145	t	71.2 km SE from Maku to Khoy, 1440 m	45.01	38.96
KU 2150	t	44.9 km N from Marand to Jolfa, 1360 m	45.60	38.76
KU 2151	t	22.8 km WNW from Mianeh to Tabriz, 1340 m	47.48	37.36
KU 2154	t	68.7 km SW from Qazvin to Hamadan, 1500 m	49.45	38.85
KU 2156	s	7.3 km SW Awej to Hamadan, 2160 m	49.15	35.55
KU 2157	t	17.6 km SE from Karand to Shahabad, 1480 m	46.41	34.16

KU 20-10	s	Iran (wp)	9 km NW of Ramsar (Chalus - Resht)	50.55	36.96
KU 2096	s		51 km W of Babulsar (Babulsar - Chalus)	52.10	36.57
KU 2102	s		52 km NW of Ramsar (Chalus - Resht)	50.17	37.18
KU 2103	s		13 km SSE of Resht (Chalus - Resht)	49.73	37.27
KU 2105	s		12 km NW of Pahlavi (Pahlavi - Astara)	49.34	37.50
KU 2107	s		12 km of Hashtpar (Pahlavi - Astara)	48.90	37.89
KU 2109	t		Astara (Pahlavi - Astara)	48.86	38.41
KU 2110	s		32 km SW of Astara (Astara - Ardabil)	48.55	38.40
KU 2126	s		Techalousse (near Chalus)	51.42	36.64
KU 2159	s		Ramsar	50.62	36.91
k 1959	s	Iran (ep)	Sari-Mazandaran, 10 m	53.04	36.57
k 1960	s		Baijan, 1100 m	52.29	35.97
KU 20-9	s		5 km W of Behshahr (Sari - Behshahr)	53.46	36.66
KU 2075	s		15 km E of Behshahr (Behshahr – Gorgan)	53.70	36.70
KU 2076	s		8 km W of Gorgan	54.35	36.82
KU 2080	s		Gharaghaj near Shahpesend (Gorgan - Hoshyeylak)	55.18	37.09

KU 2081	s		NE of Koshyailagh (Gorgan - Koshyailagh)	55.45	36.94
KU 2083	s		Koshyailagh	55.35	36.82
KU 2087	t		15 km NE of Sari (Sari - Behshahr)	53.19	36.48
k 426	t	Turkmenistan	Kara-Kala d., Bahchi, 540 m	56.62	38.41
k 427	t		Kizil-Atrek d., Meshhet-Missarian plateau	54.78	37.64
k 428	t		Kara-Kala d., the road from Yari-Kala v. to Shermop, 320 m	56.32	38.38
k 429	t		Kara-Kala d., W Kopet-Dag, Kara-Su gorge, 720 m	56.75	38.42
k 433	s		Central Kopet-Dag, Baharden d., Nuhur, Koyne-Gumberg v., 1200 m	57.03	38.47
k 1345	t		Chardzhou region, Charshanga d., K. Marks collective farm, 1600 m	66.67	37.96
k 1560	t		Ashkhabad d., Firyuza gorge	58.09	37.92
k 1561	t		Bolshoy Balhan mountain ridge	54.40	39.58
k 1563	t		Maliy Balhan mountain ridge, the river-head of Chal-Su spring	55.02	39.31
k 1903	t		Kara-Kala d., Keshi-Yol mountain	56.50	38.45
AE 213	s		Syunt-Hasardag mountain ridge, Mezetli mountains, 1400 m	56.58	38.54

k 963	t	Afghanistan	Kabul, the road Kabul – Lonchar, 1850 m	69.14	34.33
k 964	t		Kabul – Kunduz road, S slope of Gindikush, before Salang pass, 1850 m	69.22	35.17
k 967	t		Kabul – Kunduz road, N of Pulihumri, 640 m	68.67	36.06
k 982	t		From Akkupruk upstream along Balh river, 760 m	66.84	36.08
k 989	t		Badgis d., 640 m	63.70	35.76
k 995	t		Great – Kushka road, 1390 m	62.13	34.58
k 998	t		Doshi – Bamian road, 940 m	68.44	35.57
KU 20-6	t	Pakistan	8 km SW of Quetta	66.97	30.10
KU 2002	t		Suburbs of Quetta	67.00	30.21
KU 2009	t		2 km E of Chaman	66.42	30.91
k 912	t	India	Kashmir, near Srinagar	74.86	34.07
k 394	t	Uzbekistan	Sir-Darya region, Zaamin d., the place Uylma	68.39	39.94
k 421	t		Tashkent region, VIR experiment station	69.25	41.33
k 1346	t		Kahka-Darya region, 370 m	65.92	38.47
k 1352	t		Surhan-Darya region, Baysun, 1250 m	67.19	38.21

k 1356	t		Surhan-Darya region, Sherabad d., 750 m	66.86	37.74
k 1805	t		Kahka-Darya region, Karshi d.	65.79	38.85
AE 955	t	Tajikistan	S Tajikistan, Gandzhina low mountain region, Gazimajlik valley, dry slope, 900 m	68.57	37.96
K 258	t		Kumsargi region, Pobeda collective farm	68.78	37.8
k 677	t	Kirgizstan	Osh region, Karasu d., Kenegi collective farm, department №4 Bogara	72.89	40.70
k 1261	t		Osh region, 39 km from Arslanbob, 890 m	72.83	41.11
k 1322	t	Kazakhstan	Chimkent region, Turkestan d., 5 km W of Kentau	68.44	43.50
k 1336	t		Dzhambul region, Lugovoy d., 8 km from Angabas, 600 m	72.39	42.97
k 1611	t		Alma-Ata region, Talgar d., 15 km from Novo-Alekseevka v., 800 m	77.22	43.41

* “t” – ssp. *tauschii*; “s” – ssp. *strangulata*

** “(c)” – continental; “(wp)” – western precaspian; “(ep)” – eastern precaspian

*** “d.” – district; “v” village